

AtlantECO Flagship Veleiro ECO

Cruise Report

ITAJAÍ RIVER AND ADJACENT COASTAL AREA

February 28 to March 8, 2023

Team on board:

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Prof^a. Dr^a. Andrea Santarosa Freire – project coordinator at UFSC - Dept. de Ecologia e Zoologia e PPG Ecologia/ UFSC

Daniel Soldatelli Murara - sailor

Dr^a. Érica Caroline Becker - researcher – PPG Ecologia/ UFSC

Oceanographer Gabriela R. Silveira – researcher and sailor – PPG Ecologia/ UFSC

Oceanographer Guilherme dos Santos Silva - researcher and sailor – PPG Oceanografia/ UFSC

Oceanographer Juliana Hayden - researcher and sailor - PPG Oceanografia/ UFSC

Oceanographer Maria Luiza S. de Oliveira – researcher - PPG Oceanografia/ UFSC

Roberto Bruno Fabiano – captain of Veleiro ECO

Campaign Objective

This campaign aimed to analyze the impact of the Itajaí River (Santa Catarina, Brazil) on the coastal zone in terms of microbiome, microplastics and biogeochemical variables. During the nine days on board, the team worked at five research stations for approximately 10 hours of work per day (Figure 1 and Table I). At each station there was an average of 85 samples collected, totaling 440 samples collected in the Itajaí River and coastal zone for genetic, taxonomic and biogeochemical analyses (Table II). In addition to the stations planned for the AtlantECO Project, extra and shorter stations were carried out, as part of the master's work of student Juliana Hayden, from the Postgraduate Course in Oceanography at UFSC, who is supervised by Prof. Alessandra Larissa Fonseca.

Mission AtlantECO
Itajaí - SC

Figure 1. Location of the sampling Stations. 1: Station #001 - Plume 2; 2: Station #002 – Plume 1; 3: Station #003 – Sea; 4: Station #004 – River; 5: Station #005 – River mouth.

Table I. Data from each research station

	Station 001 Plume 2	Station 002 Plume 1	Station 002 Plume 1	Station 003 Sea	Station 003 Sea (day after)	Station 004 River	Station 004 River	Station 005 River mouth
Geographical coordinates	S 26° 52.704' W 48° 34.398'	S 26° 52.920' W 48° 37.212'	S 26° 52.920' W 48° 37.212'	S 26° 52.938' W 48° 31.062'	S 26° 52.938' W 48° 31.062'	S 26° 52.464' W 48° 41.346'	S 26° 52.464' W 48° 41.346'	S 26° 54.390' W 48° 37.068'
	S 26.8784 W 48.5733	S 26.882 W 48.6202	S 26.882 W 48.6202	S 26.8823 W 48.5177	S 26.8823 W 48.5177	S 26.8744 W 48.6891	S 26.8744 W 48.6891	S 26.9065 W 48.6178
Date	02/03/2023	03/03/2023		04/03/2023	05/03/2023	06/03/2023	06/03/2023	07/03/2023
Start time (UTC)	13:55	14:18		15:50	16:30	13:00	19:36	13:20
End time (UTC)	21:25	22:28		19:00	22:00	16:30	23:15	18:30
Station depth	17 m	10 m		38 m	38 m	8,5 m	8,5 m	9 m
Sampling depth	Z00	Z00	Z001 - 5m	Z00	Z00 e Z001 - 15 m	Z00	Z00	Z00
Tide	Ebb	Ebb				Flood	Ebb	Ebb*
Secchi Disc	1,25 m	2,25 m		11,25 m	3,5 m	0,20 m	0,20 m	???
Temperature (°C)	27	28		30	29,5	25	26	25
Salinity	25	23		32,5	28	0	0	22
Cast CTD	No number, only cast of this day	ST_001	ST_001_2	Cast # 42	cast # 47	cast # 50	cast # 52	cast # 53

Table II. Samples collected from each protocol at each research station and total samples obtained for analysis in the expedition. Number in red: 3 of each are from surface samples (Z000) and one of each from Z001.

PROTOCOLS	Station 001 Plume 2	Station 002 Plume 1	Station 002 Plume 1	Station 003 Sea	Station 003 Sea (day after)	Station 004 River	Station 004 River	Station 005 River mouth	TOTAL
CHLOA	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	7
eDNA	1	1	1	1		0	1	1	6
HG Amuminum	1	1	1	1		0	1	1	6
PM Aluminium	1	1	1	1		0	1	1	6
S320	3	3	1	0	4	3	0	3	17
S023	3	3	1	0	4	3	0	3	17
S<02	3	3	1	0	4	3	0	3	17
P320	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	7
P023	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	7
SG-1, 2, 3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	24
FC-P e FC-G	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	16
HC-1, 2, 3, 4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	32
SEM	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
FCAM 20 (horizontal)	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
FM20 (horizontal)	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
LU20 (horizontal)	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
E20 (horizontal)	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
S20 (horizontal)	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
S20-L (horizontal)	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
PM20 (horizontal)	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
FCAM 20 (vertical)	1	1			1	1	1	1	6
FM20 (vertical)	1	1			1	0	1	0	4
LU20 (vertical)	1	1			1	1	1	1	6
E20 (vertical)	1	1			1	0	1	1	5
S20 (vertical)	1	1			1	0	1	1	5
S20-L (vertical)	1	1			1	0	1	1	5
PM20 (vertical)	1	1			1	1	1	1	6
FM200	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
ET200	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
E200	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
S200	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
S200-L	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
PM200	1	1		1		1	1	1	6
SP330	2	9		2		19	19	19	70
MP330	1	2		0		3	0	1	7
CP300 (modified)	1	1				1	1	1	5
IRA	1	1	0	1	0		1	1	5
DIC	1	1	1	2	2		2	2	11
AT	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	7
NUT	3	3	3	3	3		3	3	21
DINO	2	2	2	2	2		2	2	14
HPLC	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
PMJ	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	7
Total number of samples	59	67	28	42	42	61	65	76	440

Expedition details

28/02/2023

Part of the team was already on board the ECO on the 27th – Érica, Guilherme and Daniel – the rest arrived on the 28th around 9:30 am (Brazilian time from now on). The UFSC materials were transported to Biguaçu on the morning of the 27th.

The team left the Marina in Biguaçu around 1:30 pm. During navigation, the team organized all materials and equipment on board.

After approximately 40 miles of navigation, we arrived in Itajaí around 6 pm.

Figure 2. Veleiro ECO moored at Itajaí Marina (photo taken on 01/03/2023)

01/03/2023

We set sail from Marina de Itajaí at around 10:30 am to make the pilot station, where all the research protocols and equipment were tested, and the interaction between the entire crew during the activities.

02/03/2023

We started navigation early, towards station #001. At this station we carried out all the protocols on the surface and at ebb tide.

03/03/2023

On this day we sail again towards the open sea towards station #002. We work with surface and 5 m deep samples, both on the ebb tide. Extra samplings were carried out for Juliana Hayden's master's research in six research stations.

04/03/2023

On this day, samplings were carried out at station #003, the farthest from the coast in this campaign. This station is approximately 11 nautical miles distant from the coast. We spent the day working with surface samples. The station was not finished due to the arrival of a storm. Protocols S320, S023, S<02, manta and net protocols of 20 um vertical haul could not be carried out and were left for the next day.

05/03/2023

Samplings were concentrated again at station #003 to finish the work started the day before. We finalize the surface sampling, described above, and then focus on sampling at Z001 – 15 m depth. Samplings were also carried out at extra stations for Juliana Hayden's research.

06/03/2023

Today the sampling was inside the Itajaí river, station #004. We work both on flood and ebb tides. It is noteworthy that, despite the tide table indicating flooding during the morning, the flow of water on the surface was towards the coastal zone. The tide was very strong throughout the day, always towards the coast, so much that we made the 200 um net and manta with the boat anchored. It was difficult to sample with the 20 um net, especially the vertical trawl. It was also difficult to deploy CTD in the water.

On that day, the ECO was supplied with 2,000 liters of diesel at the Kowalsky gas station, in partnership with the UNIVALI Oceanographic Museum. In addition to the AtlantECO station, two Juliana Hayden research stations were made.

07/03/2023

On this day, the survey was carried out at the mouth of the Itajaí River, station #005, close to the port channel. Due to the large number of vessels entering and leaving the port and the large swell at the mouth of the river, we moved a little north, towards the plume, where we were able to work anchored. Again, despite the tide table indicating flooding during the morning, the surface water flow was towards the coastal zone. For this reason, we discarded the sampling at flood tide and did it only in the ebb tide. In addition to the AtlantECO station, we made some Juliana Hayden stations. **IMPORTANT**: any logsample or sample from this station (#005) that may have been recorded as flood is actually ebb! We work only on the surface.

08/03/2023

We set sail from the Itajaí Marina around 7:30 am to Biguaçu.

CTD profiles at research stations

Station #001 – Plume 2 – morning cast:

Station #001 – Plume 2 – afternoon cast:

Station #002 – Plume 1:

Station #003 – Sea – first day of station:

Station #003 – Sea – second day of station:

Station #004 – River:

Station #005 – River mouth:

SBE19plus_01907422_2023_03_07_0053.hex: Station #005 - River Mouth

